

Spectral properties of inorganic-organic films on glass

**Alfonz Plško¹, Katarína Faturíková¹, Jana Pagáčová², Iveta Papučová²,
Mariana Švančárková¹**

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

² Faculty of Industrial Technologies in Púchov, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, I. Krasku 491/30,
SK-020 01 Púchov, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

In the first part of given report, the properties of light and its interaction with environment are closely discussed. The light reflection and refractive index of dielectric, in our case of glass, are defined and the spectral properties of „air/film/glass“ system are described. The main emphasis is given on the utilisation of reflectometry for calculation of optical characteristics of films deposited on glass surface. The studied optical characteristics were refractive index of film and its geometric thickness. It was found that for calculation of studied characteristics of film on glass, the Eq. (1) can be used while the conditions hereinafter are valid.

At vertical incidence of light to glass with thin film, the following equation which is valid for reflectance (ρ) of thin non-absorbing coating on glass and monochromatic radiation is defined:

$$\rho = \frac{n_1^2(n-n_0)^2 \cos^2 \frac{x}{2} + (n_1^2 - n_0n)^2 \sin^2 \frac{x}{2}}{n_1^2(n+n_0)^2 \cos^2 \frac{x}{2} + (n_1^2 + n_0n)^2 \sin^2 \frac{x}{2}} \quad (1)$$

where n_0 , n_1 and n is refractive index of air, coating and glass, respectively

and $x = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} n_1 d \cos \varphi_1$, where d is physical thickness of coating, φ_1 is angle of beam incidence; in our case $\varphi_1 \sim 0$.

For practical usage for measurement of reflection spectra of films prepared by sol-gel method, the two approach were compared:

„One-side“ method

- It means that sample of glass or glass with film is edged (roughened) and covered by matt black coating on one side
- During the measurement of reflection spectrum, the reflection at back side of sample is minimized and the effect of absorption in sample is minimized too
- Obtained reflection spectrum is considered as spectrum of „air/glass“ or „air/film/glass“ system

„Two-side“ method

- It means that sample of glass or glass with film on both sides is measured without surface modification
- Reflection spectrum is obtained in „air/glass/air“ or „air/film/glass/film/glas/air“ system

Table 1. The comparison of „One-side“ method and „Two-side“ method

Property	One-side method	Two-side method
<i>Film</i>	AD19002Ba	jAD19002Ba
Refractive index	1.49898	1.51740
Standard deviation	$1.92538 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.63932 \cdot 10^{-4}$
<i>Film</i>	AD19026Va	jAD19026Va
Refractive index	1.44550	1.44681
Standard deviation	$3.47873 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.31993 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Thickness /nm/	97.5864	97.0998
Standard deviation /nm/	$9.60973 \cdot 10^{-1}$	1.52579
<i>Film</i>	AD19026Vb	jAD19026Vb
Refractive index	1.44837	1.44640e
Standard deviation	$1.92538 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$7.42460 \cdot 10^{-3}$
Thickness /nm/	97.5081	94.5686
Standard deviation /nm/	$7.81980 \cdot 10^{-1}$	1.58078
<i>Film</i>	TiA19001B	jTiA19001B
Refractive index	1.49840	1.50479
Standard deviation	$4.01376 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.61682 \cdot 10^{-4}$
<i>Film</i>	TiA19008Va	jTiA19008Va
Refractive index	2.37677	2.34183
Standard deviation	$3.67272 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.59529 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Thickness /nm/	108.351	106.491
Standard deviation /nm/	$6.37966 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$6.50496 \cdot 10^{-1}$
<i>Film</i>	TiA19008Vb	jTiA19008Vb
Refractive index	2.37175	2.37706
Standard deviation	$5.99867 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$6.51231 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Thickness /nm/	107.791	108.756
Standard deviation /nm/	$7.15622 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$8.17148 \cdot 10^{-1}$

On the basis of results, which are shown in Table 1, it can be concluded that observed differences between „One-side“ method and „Two-side“ method are minimal. It allows to use the „Two-side“ method for determination of refractive index and thickness of film, because the given method is significantly faster and less difficult for preparation of samples for measurement.

Keywords: sol-gel, inorganic-organic nanocomposite films, spectral properties, index of refraction, thickness

Acknowledgment:

This presentation was created in the frame of the project New materials and technologies for industry in 21st. centuries , ITMS code is 313011T546, operational program Research and innovation, co-funded from European Regional Development Fund.